

SOME APPLICATIONS OF COMPOSITES IN COMMERCIAL AIRCRAFT COMPONENTS

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In recent years composites with polymeric and metallic matrices and various reinforcing fibres (boron, carbon, glass, organic) have been created and thoroughly investigated. The comparison of new materials with the traditional ones according to the main properties, such as density, elastic modulus, long-term and short-term strength, and also according to some structural parameters shows their superiority over traditional materials used in aircraft engineering.

Local strengthening of metallic structures is a rational way of using composites, where the most effective realization of unidirectional composites high mechanical properties is possible, thus providing weight reduction by 20-50% with simultaneous increase of the structure stiffness and vibration strength.

The other effective application of composites is their use in sandwich structure skins. The specific strength of such skins is 1.5 - 2 times as much compared to aluminium skins.

The aircraft control surface structures: rudders, flaps, slats, interceptors, hatch doors, etc., produced as sandwich structures with honeycomb, corrugated or tubular fillers and having skins of carbon-and-boron fibre reinforced plastics provide the components weight reduction from 12 to 40%. The use of sheet carbon-and-organic fibre reinforced plastics in combination with polymeric paper or glass cloth base honeycombs for floor panels and bulkheads provides weight reduction of structure 1 m^2 by 20-30% and also comfort improvement as the result of vibration and noise level reduction in the salon.